

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

О РЕАЛЬНОЙ РЕЛИГИОЗНОЙ СИТУАЦИИ В ДОИСЛАМСКИХ РЕГИОНАХ СЕМИРЕЧЬЯ И ТЕНГИР-ТОО ПОСЛЕ АТЛАХСКОГО СРАЖЕНИЯ 751 Г.: (СЕРЕДИНА VIII – СЕРЕДИНА XII ВВ.)

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ON THE REAL RELIGIOUS SITUATION IN THE PRE-ISLAMIC REGIONS OF JETI-SUU (SEMIRECHYE) AND TENGIR-TOO (TIAN-SHAN) AFTER THE 751 BATTLE OF ATLAKH: (MID-8TH – MID-12TH CENTURIES)

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена изучению основных источников битвы при Атлахе (в Таласской долине) 751 г. н.э. и проблемам религиозно-исторической оценки этого события. Некоторые авторы предполагают, что после битвы при Атлахе ислам стал абсолютной господствующей религией. Однако автор статьи подчеркивает, что большинство тюркских народов в горных долинах Тенгир-Тоо (Тянь-Шань) приняли ислам только в X в., во времена Караханидского каганата, и что это мусульманское государство было многоконфессиональным, среди его населения проживали также язычники, христиане, тенгрианцы, манихеи и другие религиозные группы.

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to study of the main sources of the Battle of Atlakh (in Talas valley) in 751 AD and the problems of religious and historical assessment of this event. Some authors have suggested that after the Battle of Atlakh, Islam became the absolute dominant religion. However, the author of the article emphasizes that most Turkic peoples in the mountainous valleys of Tengir-Too (Tian-Shan) converted to Islam only in the 10th century, during the Karakhanid Khaganate, and that this Muslim state was multi-religious, with pagans, Christians, Theologians, Manichaeans, and other religious groups also living among its population.

Ключевые слова: тюрк, Китай, Великий Шелковый путь, Внутренняя Азия, Центральная Азия, Атлах, Талас, этнические отношения, религия.

Keywords: Turkic, China, Great Silk Road, Inner Asia, Central Asia, Atlakh, Talas, Ethnic Relations, Religion.

Introduction

In the summer of 2025, exactly 1,274 years had passed since the famous Battle of Atlakh in the Talas Valley. By the way, in connection with this battle, the academic community of Talas State University (TalSU) organized an international scientific conference entitled “The Battle of Talas and Its Historical Significance” on September 10, 2021, which was a commendable initiative about the almost forgotten historical event. [24; p. 123]

However, some contemporaries, eager to claim the event for their own, mistakenly believe that the history of the Battle of Atlakh belongs exclusively either to Kyrgyzstan or to Kazakhstan, or concerns only these two countries. [See criticism: 24, p.123–124]

The battle took place near the medieval town of Atlakh, which was surrounded by walls and had mosques, markets, and gardens. According to modern Kyrgyz and Kazakh archaeologists, the ruins of the ancient town of Atlakh near the Talas River correspond to the archaeological site of Joon-Töbö, located in the Kyrgyzstan territory to the south of the current Kyrgyz-Kazakh border. This site lies within the village area of

Keñesh, Manas District, Talas Region, Kyrgyzstan. The distinguished Kazakh archaeologist and academician Karl Moldakhmetovich Baipakov (1940–2018) also confirmed that the Joon-Töbö archaeological site corresponds to the ancient city of Atlakh [2, p. 341].

In the 1950s, a Kyrgyzstani archaeologist Pyotr Nikitovich Kozhemyako (1918–1973) was the first to conduct excavations at this site [14, pp. 7–11; 15, pp. 145–224]. Unfortunately, subsequent agricultural development during the centrally planned Soviet economy caused great damage to the preservation of the ruins. A petroglyphic inscription found at this site contains the word “Atlakh” (Atlay) written in runic-like Bitig script, deciphered by the Russian Turkologist Sergei Grigoryevich Klyashtorny (1928–2014) [12, pp. 289–290; 25, p. 8].

However, the history of the Battle of Atlakh is not merely a local issue of Kyrgyzstan or Kazakhstan — it is a key chapter in the broader parts of Central and Eastern Eurasian history. This is because the battle was one of the turning points affecting the destinies of the Far East, Central Asia, and the Near East. [24, p. 118]

Just as the 451 Battle of the Catalaunian Plains under Attila influenced not only the European Huns and the declining Roman Empire, but also the whole history of Western and Central Europe, and just as the 1789 French Revolution affected all of Western and Eastern Europe, so too did the 751 Battle of Atlakh leave a profound mark on the interconnected regions of the Near East, Central Asia, Inner Asia, and East Asia along the Great Silk Road. [25, p. 10–11]

On the Primary Sources

Information about the era of the Battle of Atlakh is preserved in the written Oriental sources. Among the Arabic sources, the chronicles of al-Tabari contain substantial data on the Umayyad and Abbasid Caliphates' campaigns into Western Central Asia, particularly into the region known as Mawarannahr (the oasis area between the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers). [28]

Abu Ja'far Muhammad ibn Jarir al-Tabari (born in 838 or 839 – died in 923), a prominent Muslim historian, writer, and theologian of the Middle Ages, was born in the province of Tabaristan (modern Iran). His Arabic-language work entitled "History of the Prophets and Kings" ('Tarikh al-Rusul wa-l-Muluk') covers events from the creation of Adam up to 915 CE. It includes precise dates for many events in Central Asia during the 7th–10th centuries [20]. However, neither al-Tabari nor any extant part of his work contains direct mention of the Battle of Atlakh in 751.

The first Muslim author to mention Atlakh and Taraz was al-Mutahhar al-Maqdisi. In 966, he wrote in Arabic his work "Kitab Bad' al-Khalq wa-l-Ta'rikh" ('The Book of the Beginning of Creation and History') in the region of Sistan (modern southeastern Iran and southwestern Afghanistan) [7, pp. 9–12; 8, pp. 50–51].

Another key source is "al-Kamil fi-t-Tarikh" ('The Complete History') written in Arabic in the 13th century by the historian 'Izz al-Din Ibn al-Athir (1160–1233/34). [31] His monumental work, published in 14 volumes by K. Tornberg in the 19th century, provides significant details about the political history of the Turkic peoples of Tian Shan, including the 751 battle near the city of Atlakh by the Talas River between the Tang army and Arab, Turkic, and Turgesh forces [18, pp. 52–76; 19, pp. 358–409; 21].

The Chinese Sources

As for Chinese sources, three major chronicles describe the Tang dynasty's relations with Central Asia in the mid-8th century and mention the Battle of Atlakh:

1. "The Old Book of Tang" ('Jiu Tang Shu'), written between 941–945 under Emperor Gaozu of the Later Jin dynasty, led by chief minister Liu Xu;

2. "The New Book of Tang" ('Xin Tang Shu'), compiled under the Song dynasty by the eminent statesman, poet, and historian Ouyang Xiu (1007–1072);

3. "Zizhi Tongjian" ('A Comprehensive Mirror to Aid in Government'), compiled by Sima Guang (1019–1086), which covers the history of China and its neighbouring states from 403 BCE to 960 CE.

The excerpts from these Chinese sources have been translated into Kyrgyz and published in Ürümqi in the Kyrgyz-style Arabic script under the editorship of Professor Mambetturdu Mambetakun [22; see also 29].

Accounts of the Battle

According to al-Mutahhar al-Maqdisi's account:

"Abu Muslim sent Ziyad ibn Salih on an expedition. Having taken the regions of Mawarannahr, he reached Taraz and Atlakh. The Chinese were alarmed and sent over 100,000 men. Sa'id ibn Humayd entrenched himself in Taraz. Abu Muslim, remaining in Samarkand, ordered aid to be sent. After several battles, the Muslims killed 45,000 of them, captured 25,000, and the rest fled..." [7, pp. 76–80; 8, pp. 50–51].

The Arabic historian Ibn al-Athir adds:

"In the year 133 AH (750–751 CE), a conflict arose between the ruler of Fergana and the ruler of Shash (Tashkent). The ruler of Fergana sought aid from the Chinese emperor, who sent 100,000 troops. They besieged Shash. The ruler of Shash surrendered, but his son appealed to the Arabs. Abu Muslim sent Ziyad ibn Salih, and near the Talas River the armies met. The Muslims killed 50,000, captured 20,000, and the rest fled to China..." [7, p. 88; 9, p. 22; 21, p. 281; 21, p. 281; 28; 32, p. 344].

The Chinese chronicles state that the Tang general Gao Xianzhi or Ko Sönji (an ethnic Korean by origin) led 30,000 troops westward, but after five days of fierce fighting, the Karluks — initially allied with the Chinese — switched sides, attacking from the rear and ensuring the Arabs' victory. General Gao Xianzhi barely escaped. It is known that the commander Gao Xianzhi was beheaded on January 24, 756, by order of the Tang emperor for another occasion. [25, p. 18]

Interpretations of the Battle

Some modern authors exaggerate the battle as a decisive clash between civilizations or claim that Islam immediately became dominant in Central Asia afterward. However, evidence shows that the Islamization of the Tian Shan Turkic peoples occurred much later — primarily during the rule of the Karakhanid Khanate in the 10th century [23, pp. 28–44].

The Karakhanid state, like its predecessors (the Western Turk, Turgesh, and Karluk khanates), was multiethnic and multireligious. Even in the 10th–12th centuries, Tengrist, pagan, Christian (Nestorian), and Manichaean communities coexisted. Archaeological and written evidence — runic inscriptions, Sogdian documents, Buddhist temples, and Chinese coins — confirms that pre-Islamic traditions persisted in the Talas, Chüy, Ili, and Naryn regions long after 751.

Arab geographers like Ibn Hawqal noted that even in the early 10th century, eastern mountainous areas such as Alay and Tian Shan were considered lands hostile to Islam, beyond which Muslims rarely ventured [8, p. 49; 23].

Moreover, the battle did not sever ties between China and Central Asia. Diplomatic missions continued — for example, Karluk envoys visited the Tang capital Chang'an in 753 CE, where they were received with honours [16, p. 43].

Thus, the 751 Battle of Atlakh did not mark a total political or cultural rupture between China and Central Asia. Rather, it reshaped alliances and shifted regional balance.

The transmission of papermaking technology from China to Samarkand after the battle is a famous

example of how intercultural exchange persisted. [25, p. 21]

A short conclusion.

The Battle of Atlakh in 751 cannot be viewed simply as a religious confrontation or the start of Islam's dominance in the region. It was a turning point in Eurasian geopolitics — one that curtailed Tang expansion westward but also stimulated ongoing diplomatic, cultural, and technological exchange across the Silk Road. [30, p. 3]

At the same time, it is also true that most Turkic peoples in the mountainous valleys of Tengir-Too (Tian-Shan) converted to Islam only in the 10th century, during the Karakhanid Khaganate. [23, pp. 28–44] However, the Sogdian scripts preserved in the Kulan-Sai (Qulan-Say) petroglyphs in the Talas valley and a lot of Muslim sources from the Karakhanid era show that this Muslim state on the edge of the so-called Golden age of Islam was a multi-religious country.

The Karakhanid Muslims had to live together with pagans, i.e. Tengrianists amongst Turkic nomadic groups. There were also local communities of the Christians (i.e. Nestorians who were related to a church separated from Byzantine Christianity after 431.). The Nestorians were called as “Tarsa” in the Turkic languages of the early Medieval times; even the famous Kyrgyz heroic epic of Manas preserved this term “Tarsa” for the Christians. There was a town called Tarsakent and situated in the Chui valley (the Karajygach archaeological site situated to the south-east of modern city of Bishkek). [21, p. 168] There were also tiny groups of Manichaeans, and other religious groups amongst the Karakhanid state's population.

There were some representatives of the Buddhists in Tengir-Too in the 8th–early 10th centuries. After the fall of the Liao dynasty of the Khitan (Qidān) people's rulers in Northern China in 1125 following the Jurchen invasion, some groups of the Khitan were forced to migrate towards the Karakhanid state via Inner Asia. In 1128 Yelü Dashi's group of the Khitans invaded the eastern parts of the Karakhanid state and established the Qara Khitai or Western Liao dynasty. They made the city of Balasagun as their capital.

Recently, in 1992, the Kyrgyz archaeologists Kubatbek Tabaldiev and Orobek Soltobayev discovered a Medieval archaeological site of Kōk-Tash near the village of Kum-Döbö in the Kochkor district of the Naryn region (in Kyrgyzstan). The excavations on the site were carried out in 2017–2018 by a team from the Kyrgyz-Turkish Manas University headed by Professor Kubatbek Tabaldiev and Dr. Künbolot Akmatov. It appeared that this was the underground tomb of the Qara Khitai. [27, p. 720–730] Thus, the Qara Khitai brought back also Buddhism into the Karakhanid part of Central Asia in results of their invasion.

Still, the Buddhists were not dominants amongst the vast population of different faiths in Central Asia which became mostly Muslim.

However, we would like to stress it again that it does not mean that the Tengir-Too Turkic peoples became the Muslims immediately after the 751 Atlakh battle. The turning point was the Karakhanid era of the inclusion of the region into the so-called Islamic

Golden age in the 10th–11th centuries when the local Turkic intellectuals such as Jusup Balasagyn, Makhmud Kashghari Barskani, etc. became champions of the Islamic culture and science while fighting for their national and ethnic identities as the Turkic members of the latest Eastern streams of the movement of shu'ubiyya (شعوبية) to oppose the privileged status of the Arabic language and culture in the Khalifat.

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